

TEACHER'S PERSPECTIVE ON THE USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ON LEARNING PROCESSES: AN EVALUATION OF EMBRACING HIGH TECHNOLOGICAL DEPENDENCE OF CURRICULUM

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Teacher's Perspective on the Use of Artificial Intelligence on Learning Processes: An Evaluation of Embracing High Technological Dependence of Curriculum

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Abstract

AI is everywhere. Popular list of various digital tools and resources that teachers and students can use in the academe, including e-learning platforms, digital pinboards, collaborative tools, and lesson planning apps. Artificial Intelligence is a booming technological domain capable of altering every aspect of social interactions. In education, AI has begun producing new teaching and learning solutions that are now undergoing testing in different contexts. AI requires advanced infrastructures and an ecosystem of thriving innovators. Additionally, it has a profound and increasingly important role in education. Its applications are transforming how education is delivered, making it more personalized, efficient, and effective. It is inevitable in the education aspect that teachers were informed and aware on how AI works. Teachers nowadays must be adaptive, flexible, and relevant in this tech driven world. AI in the education sector provides personalization, automation, accessibility, and data-driven insights. These features contribute to improved learning outcomes, increased teacher efficiency, and a more responsive and effective education system, ultimately benefiting students and educators alike. To address the research gaps, this study explores the status, challenges and future directions of AI in teaching practice. Since the field of AI-based instruction is still developing, this study can contribute to the development of comprehensive AI-based instruction that allow teachers to participate in the working process.

Keywords: *teachers perspectives, artificial intelligence, technological dependence*

Introduction

At present, due to the rapid advancements in global science and technology, AI technology has made significant progress. AI technology is constantly evolving and has become widely adopted across different industries (Zhang, 2021). As an evolving idea in the field, AI has been defined as "the ability of a digital computer or computer-controlled robot to perform tasks commonly associated with intelligent beings" (Britannica, 2023). This specific definition emphasizes the imitation of human behavior and consciousness. In addition, AI has been described as the integration of various technologies that enable machines to perform tasks such as cognitive automation, machine learning, reasoning, hypothesis generation and analysis, natural language processing, and intentional algorithm mutation, resulting in the ability to generate insights and analytics that rival or surpass human capabilities. By combining these definitions, one can describe artificial intelligence as a technology that constructs systems capable of thinking and behaving like humans, with the capacity to accomplish goals. And with so much advantage, it is clear that AI has become more prevalent in schools, integrating into the educational environment and teaching process. AI has been extensively utilized in the education sector and has demonstrated significant benefits in terms of application. Its impact on the teaching process and classroom management has been profound, as highlighted by various studies (Chassignol, Khoroshavin, Klimova, & Bilyatdinova, 2018; Roll & Wylie, 2016). Growing body of researches on AI and education shows utilization of AI technology to support teaching, create smart campuses, and enable intelligent learning, teaching, and management. Applying cutting-edge technologies like image recognition, face recognition, and adaptive learning to the education field has sparked a wave of transformations. These advancements have not only enhanced the efficiency of teachers' work but also elevated students' learning experience.

A recent study highlights the significant impact of artificial intelligence on enhancing the quality of education in various ways (Choi, 2020). AI-driven learning methods have been utilized to assess students' performance records, identify their areas of expertise and areas for improvement, and deliver personalized learning experiences that cater to their unique requirements. This approach offers students a model that equips them with the necessary tools to enhance their knowledge and achieve productive results (Aldosari, 2020). AI-based technology, including Chatbots, Virtual Assistance tools, and Adaptive Learning Systems, provide students with immersive and engaging learning experiences. These technologies enable students to explore complex theories and solutions in a more interactive and meaningful way (Chaudhry et al., 2023; Pradana, Elisa and Syarifuddin, 2023). It has been observed that the current approach to teaching, which relies on traditional methods that are not tailored to individual learning preferences, fails to effectively engage students. As a result, students' active participation and critical thinking skills may be hindered (Kistyanto et al., 2022). In order to address these gaps, the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) becomes a crucial solution.

Recent studies have shown that the integration of AI in education has resulted in more personalized, engaging, and effective learning experiences for students (Li et al., 2021). This exciting exploration of AI greatly enhances the effectiveness and involvement of educators. Given the multifaceted responsibilities of teaching staff, including administrative and academic duties, it is crucial to find ways to streamline their workload. One potential solution is the integration of AI technology, which can automate various administrative tasks like grading assignments, monitoring attendance, and offering feedback to students (Bisen et al., 2021).

Similarly, AI-powered chatbots provide learners with instant and personalized support for their academic and organizational requirements. They can answer questions about course materials, provide information on course registration, and address basic inquiries. These systems effectively analyze student data to anticipate which students may face challenges in their academic journey or potentially drop out.

While AI-enabled learning supports offer great potential, the widespread use of technology in education does not automatically mean that teachers are able to effectively use technology in the classroom or that the quality of teaching is guaranteed. This is because teachers are still in the process of being fully prepared to implement AI-based education. In addition, it has been argued by scholars that the effective integration of new instructional technologies is strongly influenced by the attitudes of the teachers who facilitate the lesson (Fernández-Batanero et al., 2021). Despite extensive research on educational technology integration, many teachers still hold negative views towards implementing technology in the classroom and are hesitant to use it (Prensky, 2008; Kaban and Ergul, 2020; Istenic et al., 2021). Instead, they persist in utilizing the identical materials and teaching methodologies, dismissing any potential approaches that could yield unfavorable results (Tallvid, 2016). In addition, the apprehension that arises from using unfamiliar technologies can be a challenge and impede teachers' endeavors to implement technology in their classrooms (Zimmerman, 2006; Hébert et al., 2021). Given the circumstances, it is crucial to understand the perspective of educators regarding the incorporation of AI into the educational curriculum. As a result, this study prompts further investigation into the viewpoints of educators regarding the integration of Artificial Intelligence into the educational experience.

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the perspective of the teachers on the utilization of AI technology on the learning process. However, specifically, it aims to:

1. Determine the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. gender; and
 - 1.3. level of technological skills?
2. Determine the acceptability level of the respondents on the utilization of AI on learning process in terms of:
 - 2.1. AI usefulness (performance expectancy); and
 - 2.2. AI ease of use (effort expectancy)?
3. Determine the perspective of the respondents on the potential challenge on the utilization of AI on the learning process.
4. Is there a significant difference between the perspective on the AI Usefulness and AI Ease of Use?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and their acceptability level?

Methodology

Research Design

The research approach selected for this study is firmly based on quantitative inquiry, especially utilizing a descriptive design to explore the intricate context of teachers' viewpoints on the incorporation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education. The primary goal of this framework is to offer an unbiased and quantitative representation of teachers' perspectives, specifically targeting their degrees of acceptance and understanding of the possible issues related to the use of AI in education. The research adopts a quantitative approach, which involves systematically collecting and analyzing numerical data using statistical tools. The study's decision to use this particular methodology highlights its dedication to producing empirical data.

The study follows the Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) and takes a comparative and correlational approach. The study aims to uncover notable disparities in the degree of acceptability of AI among instructors, specifically in terms of its perceived utility and simplicity of use. This comparison component is clearly obvious in the research. The study aims to investigate potential relationships between the respondents' characteristics and their levels of acceptance towards AI, while also considering the correlational dimension. The study aims to provide a detailed understanding by combining various methodological aspects. It will not only analyze the numerical differences but also explore the complex relationship between instructors' qualities and their views towards AI in education. This complete methodology is ready to provide useful insights to the discussion about incorporating AI in educational environments.

Respondents

The study's participants comprise a specific cohort of 40 secondary education teachers from various schools in the province of Nueva Ecija. The participants are carefully chosen using a stratified sampling procedure, which is a systematic process that improves the representativeness of the sample.

The stratified sample design involves dividing the whole population of secondary education teachers in Nueva Ecija into several subgroups, or strata, based on the schools they are affiliated with. Eight schools have been designated as the stratum in this case, guaranteeing a thorough depiction of the educational environment in the province. Within each chosen school category, a methodical procedure is utilized to choose five instructors as participants, guaranteeing a fair and varied representation of viewpoints within each

school. This methodology not only streamlines the process of gathering data effectively but also protects against any biases that may emerge from excessive dependence on a given educational institution or a particular subset of educators. In addition, the investigation deliberately incorporates teachers from several grade levels to augment the dependability and comprehensiveness of the findings. This guarantees that ideas are not limited to a particular group but rather encompass a wider range of experiences and viewpoints throughout various phases of secondary school.

Instrument

The instrument was designed with the base concept of TAM and UTAUT theory, as proposed by Davis (1989) and Venkatesh et al. (2003), respectively. These theories offer valuable frameworks for comprehending users' adoption and utilization of technology in the field of education. Three subtopics were derived from the aforementioned standard operating procedure (SOP). The researcher has devised a collection of 15 statements/questions to assess different facets of AI technology within the context of education.

The first phase of the study focuses on gathering demographic data in order to understand the background characteristics of the instructors participating in the research. Section 2 examines the level of acceptance of AI technologies based on their usefulness and ease of use. Section 3, however, is dedicated to elucidating the challenges that arise while engaging with AI. The questionnaire employs a 4-point Likert-type scale to provide a thorough and detailed analysis of responses. Participants are directed to indicate their level of agreement with each statement, on a scale that spans from 1 for strongly disagree to 4 for strongly agree.

Procedure

Within the scope of this inquiry, the data collection technique has been devised to align with the research objectives and ensure the acquisition of relevant information. Initially, the inquiry It is advisable to begin cooperation with the education departments of selected public secondary schools situated in the province of Nueva Ecija. This would entail explaining the aims of the investigation and seeking consent from the chosen participants.

Data Analysis

This study will utilize several statistical approaches to fully examine the collected data. The respondents' socio-demographic profile will be clarified by employing frequency distribution and percentage calculations, providing a precise and descriptive representation of the collected data. The utilization of the Likert scale and ranking system will be crucial in presenting the ranks of the evaluations given by participants, so facilitating a nuanced comprehension of their viewpoints. To improve the precision of the description, the Likert scale will be utilized. The weighted mean will be employed to scale the data on the questionnaire, offering a systematic technique to analyzing the respondents' impressions in accordance with appropriate legends.

The Pearson Correlation Coefficient will be utilized to evaluate the connections between variables, especially examining the possible linkages between respondents' profiles and their levels of acceptance towards AI. Furthermore, the Analysis of Variation (ANOVA) or the mean comparison tool will be used to see if there are significant variations in acceptability levels about the effectiveness and simplicity of use of AI as an educational tool. These statistical tools jointly enhance the analysis by providing a thorough and detailed assessment of the research topics.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher made every endeavor to provide thorough information about the investigation, guaranteeing total transparency about the anticipated aims, procedures, and findings. The researcher provided participants with informed permission papers, explicitly stating that their involvement was voluntary, their data would remain secret, and they may withdraw from the study without repercussions. Consequently, it is essential to provide self-administered questionnaires to a specific group of participants, which should include the first page for collecting demographic information, as well as other parts. After retrieval of questionnaire, the researcher then proceeds to the tabulation of the data gathered and then data analysis.

Results and Discussion

This section present analyzed, and interpreted the data gathered using appropriated statistical tools. This presentation is sorted with the specific questions presented on the rationale of this study. The data were presented in the tabular form.

Profile of the Respondents

By Age

Table 1. *Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age*

Age	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
21-30 years old	21	52.5 %	1
31-40 years old	11	27.5 %	2
41-50 years old	6	15 %	3
50 years old and above	2	5 %	4
Total	40	100 %	

Table 1 presents an in-depth description of the age distribution of the participants in the survey. The age group of 21-30 years old is the most prevalent among the questioned respondents, with a frequency of 21, accounting for 52.5% of the total participants. Out of the total sample, 11 respondents, accounting for 27.5%, fall within the age range of 31-40 years old. Teachers in the age group of 41-50 years account for 15% of the total responses. Finally, teachers who are 50 years old and older make up 5% of the participants. The distribution of ages in the teaching community is broad, which guarantees a wide range of opinions and inclusivity. The prevalence of educators aged 21-30 implies that this group might have a substantial impact on influencing perspectives about the incorporation of AI in education.

By Sex

Table 2. *Profile of the Respondents in terms of Sex*

Sex	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Male	18	45 %	2
Female	22	55 %	1
Total	40	100 %	

Table 2 displays the distribution of respondents' sex. Out of the 40 responders, the majority are female, with a frequency of 22, making up 55% of the overall population. Conversely, there are 18 male respondents, accounting for 45% of the participants. The gender distribution in the academic community is generally balanced, which enables a thorough exploration of varied perspectives.

Technological Capability

Table 3. *Profile of the Respondents in terms of Technological Capability*

Level	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Basic Innovative	2	5 %	4
Basic Operation	15	37.5 %	2
Intermediate Operation	18	45 %	1
Advanced Operation	5	12.5 %	3
Total	40	100 %	

Table 3 presents a comprehensive analysis of the technological skills demonstrated by the participants in this study. 45% of instructors had intermediate operating abilities at Level 3, indicating a significant group with a solid understanding of technology features. 37.5% of the responders demonstrate fundamental operating capabilities at Level 2, indicating a significant number of instructors with basic technical abilities.

Furthermore, a notable proportion of 12.5% of the instructors have advanced operational abilities at degree 4, showing a distinguished cohort with a commendable degree of expertise in employing technology. Finally, Level 1, which denotes the most basic technological proficiency, is exhibited by 5% of the individuals, occurring twice. The varied distribution of technological skills among the participants highlights the importance of careful analysis when examining instructors' viewpoints on incorporating AI in education. The diverse proficiency levels might impact the willingness and flexibility of educators to embrace AI tools and technology in the educational domain.

Acceptability Level on AI Utilization

In terms of Usefulness

Table 4. *Acceptability Level on AI Utilization in terms of Usefulness*

Items	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
Using AI in teaching would enable me to accomplish tasks more quickly.	3.77	Strongly Agree	1
Using AI would improve my job performance in teaching and administrative tasks.	3.12	Agree	6
Using AI in teaching would increase my productivity	3.25	Strongly Agree	5
Using AI would enhance the creativeness/personalization of my teaching.	2.96	Agree	7
I would find AI effectively in giving performance tasks and activities	2.54	Agree	9
I would find AI helpful in sharing or creating access to a variety of learning resources	3.47	Strongly Agree	2
I would find AI helpful in promoting students' engagement in learning activities	2.51	Agree	10
I would find AI helpful in monitoring submission of output.	3.46	Strongly Agree	3
I would find AI helpful in assessment and evaluation of outputs.	3.30	Strongly Agree	4
I would find AI useful in overall teaching process.	2.57	Agree	8
Overall Mean	3.10	Agree	

Legend: 1.00- 1.74 (Strongly Disagree) 1.75- 2.49 (Disagree) 2.50-3.24 (Agree) 3.25-4.00 (Strongly Agree)

Table 4 presents the findings concerning the acceptability level of respondents regarding the application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education, specifically focusing on its perceived usefulness. The verbal interpretation of "strongly agree" is evident in the highest

Weighted Mean (WM) of 3.77, indicating that teachers strongly agree that incorporating AI in teaching enhances task efficiency. Subsequently, with a WM of 3.47, educators express a strong agreement that AI proves beneficial in facilitating access to a diverse array of learning resources. The survey also reveals a strong consensus (WM of 3.46 and 3.30) among educators regarding the usefulness of AI in monitoring submissions and assessing outputs. Another significant finding is the WM of 3.25, suggesting a strong agreement among educators that the integration of AI in teaching would lead to increased productivity. These outcomes align with previous studies, such as Teng, Zhang, and Sun (2022), which emphasize the positive impact of AI on teaching and learning, enhancing efficiency and improving student outcomes.

Moreover, the empirical findings are corroborated by Chatterjee and Bhattacharjee (2020b), who affirm that teachers hold a positive attitude regarding the performance expectancy of AI in education. The study emphasizes the perceived benefits of AI as a valuable tool for enhancing teaching and learning outcomes, fostering student engagement, and increasing overall efficiency. AI-based systems, as explored in past studies, offer multifaceted opportunities in learning and instruction, from facilitating student collaboration to providing personalized learning experiences and managing learning activities with adaptive feedback. Furthermore, AI is also said to have the capacity to improve evaluation techniques in traditional classrooms by providing immediate and accurate information on students' educational advancement, accomplishments, or obstacles. It is feasible to do this by examining their learning patterns through thorough data analysis (Sánchez-Prieto et al., 2020).

Various research and papers have presented data to substantiate the idea that AI technologies can also handle the time-consuming administrative activities associated with teaching and learning without affecting the quality of these tasks (Chen, Chen & Lin, 2020; Felix, 2020; UNESCO, 2021). According to a survey conducted by McKinsey & Company in 2020, instructors dedicate up to 15% of their time to these specific duties. Employing AI technology for these duties can optimize time management, enabling teachers to concentrate on attending to students' educational requirements. In addition, AI may aid teachers in evaluating students by utilizing advancements in natural language processing. This enables the implementation of many applications, including plagiarism detection, assessment scoring, and automated feedback providing (Chen, Chen & Lin, 2020; Goksel and Bozkurt, 2019). AI technologies, due to their reliance on algorithms and data, have the capability to offer feedback that is more impartial and effective in comparison to human teachers (Celik, Dindar, Muukkonen & Järvelä, 2022; Terzopoulos & Satratzemi, 2019). Moreover, monitoring the educational advancement of a cohort of pupils might provide difficulties for educators. Nevertheless, AI can enhance this domain by facilitating more efficient supervision of students' educational advancement. AI technology in language teaching have facilitated a student-centered approach and enhanced learner autonomy by enabling students to track their own learning progress using AI-assisted systems (Pokrivcakova, 2019).

In general, the findings of the 3.10 WM study demonstrate a favorable degree of acceptance about the usage of AI, namely in terms of its efficacy.

In terms of Ease of Use

Table 5. *Acceptability Level on AI Utilization in terms of Ease of Use*

<i>Items</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Learning to operate AI would be easy for me.	1.98	Disagree	8
I would find it easy to understand how to use AI to do what I want to do.	2.52	Agree	5
My interaction with AI would be clear and understandable.	2.56	Agree	4
It would be easy for me to become skillful at using AI technology into teaching.	1.82	Disagree	9
I find AI technology easy to use and manipulate.	2.37	Disagree	7
I would find AI interface user-friendly.	2.61	Agree	2
I would find features of AI easy to manipulate.	2.57	Agree	3
AI has a contemporary design that facilitates adaptable accessibility	2.37	Disagree	6
AI technology has a straightforward format.	2.77	Agree	1
I find AI not vulnerable for software errors.	1.56	Strongly Disagree	10
Overall Mean	2.34	Disagree	

Legend: 1.00- 1.74 (Strongly Disagree) 1.75- 2.49 (Disagree) 2.50-3.24 (Agree) 3.25-4.00 (Strongly Agree)

Table 5 displays the results about the level of acceptance among respondents for the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education, with a special emphasis on its perceived user-friendliness. According to the respondents, AI technology has a clear and uncomplicated framework, as shown by a weighted mean (WM) of 2.77. Ranked second with a weighted mean of 2.61, the respondents also concur that they would see the AI interface as user-friendly. Rank 3 has a weighted mean (WM) of 2.57, indicating that educators find it simple to alter. However, it is worth noting that this study emphasizes that WM levels are too low. According to the survey, conducted on a sample of 1.56 respondents, AI is perceived as susceptible to software faults, as evidenced by its ranking of 10. In addition, respondents numbered 9 and 10 express their disagreement over the ease of learning to operate AI firsthand. They also disagree with the notion that it would be easy for them to become proficient in utilizing AI, particularly in the context of teaching. The research conducted by Alkhawaldeh and Menchaca (2014) identified lack of competence and confidence as significant barriers. Prior digital experience and understanding are necessary for a more rapid adaption to new technology. In order to use digital tools proficiently, it is imperative to

possess a basic comprehension of computer system operations, spreadsheet usage, word processing, internet navigation, and other browsing tools. Additionally, one must be familiar with software installation and removal procedures, as well as the customization of settings. Tarman et al., (2019) explore novel strategies and techniques for incorporating technology into educational practices. To guarantee good outcomes, educators must possess proficiency in utilizing certain technologies, such as computers, before incorporating them into their courses using appropriate strategies. Added to this, factors such as complexity, portability, technological failures, and a comprehensive understanding of the technology can significantly impede the rapid adoption of a technology (Elangovan et al., 2021). Although there are technological solutions available for many academic projects, not all of them can be completed online. Disseminating skill-based training that necessitates the utilization of physical equipment and entails a practical element is challenging.

Overall, the respondents' average rating of 2.34 WM indicates a low degree of acceptance for the ease of use of AI in the context of education.

Potential Challenges Utilizing AI

Table 6. *Potential Challenges in Utilizing AI*

Challenges	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
Lack of experience and proper training in using AI	3.75	Strongly Agree	1
Limited internet access and resources refrain from using AI	3.56	Strongly Agree	2
Lack of confidence and motivation to use AI	3.23	Agree	3
Ethical and safety issues from collecting data.	3.17	Agree	5
AI causing less interaction and less effectiveness of learning on student.	3.21	Agree	4

Legend: 1.00- 1.74 (Strongly Disagree) 1.75- 2.49 (Disagree) 2.50-3.24 (Agree) 3.25-4.00 (Strongly Agree)

Table 6 outlines the possible obstacles that educators may face while using AI into their teaching practices. The most significant problem among the many criteria is the deficiency of expertise and adequate training in utilizing AI, as seen by the highest weighted mean score of 3.75. On the second rank, the educators likewise strongly concur with a weighted mean of 3.56 that there is a restricted availability of internet access and resources, which might hinder their use of AI technologies. These findings are substantiated and connected with contemporary research on artificial intelligence. Tarman et al. (2019) found that a sluggish Internet connection posed a substantial barrier to the successful integration of technology. A lack of technical assistance discourages teachers from incorporating technology in the classroom. They also agreed that the primary obstacle to integrating ICT in classrooms is the insufficient availability of technical support and maintenance in schools (Raman, K., & Yamat, cited by Yuk Chan 2023). As per several research (Elangovan et al., 2021), the primary hindrance to effectively using technology in education is a deficiency of technical expertise. These findings emphasize the significance of incorporating awareness, training, and learning initiatives inside institutions to effectively incorporate new technologies into the company. These findings further corroborate the prior research conducted by Beerkens (2022), which revealed a significant need for more training and educational programs pertaining to the utilization of artificial intelligence in the field of education.

Conversely, the respondents also concur that the absence of motivation, ethical and safety concerns related to data collection, and less engagement might pose possible challenges in harnessing AI. The literature extensively recognizes lack of confidence as the primary and most widespread obstacle to the incorporation of technology (Kim et al., cited by Yuk Chan 2023). Research indicates that teachers expressed concerns about the potential erosion or devaluation of their conventional pedagogical approaches due to the increasing integration of computers in the classroom, which they feared may jeopardize their professional standing. The issues mentioned encompassed concerns about their ability to proficiently carry out computer-related duties and the potential for experiencing social humiliation when working with computers (Alkhalwaleh & Menchaca, 2014). The familiarity and efficacy of the conventional approach engender a reluctance to embrace new technologies, as demonstrated by Elangovan et al. (2021).

Significant difference between Acceptability Level on Usefulness and Ease of Use

Table 7. *Significant Difference between Acceptability Level on Usefulness and Ease of Use*

Summary						
Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance		
PU	10	30.95	3.095	0.193361		
PEU	10	23.13	2.313	0.154934		
Anova						
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	3.05762	1	3.05762	17.55762	0.00055	4.413873
Within Groups	3.13466	18	0.174148			
Total	6.19228	19				

The utilization of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) resulted in a significant f-ratio value of 17.55762, with a p-value of .00055. Upon comparing the p-value to the specified significance threshold of .05, it is apparent that the result is statistically significant, resulting in the rejection of the null hypothesis (Ho). This rejection indicates a significant difference between the means being compared. Upon

examination of the data, it is evident that the average score for perceived usefulness (PU) is higher than that of perceived ease of use (PEU). This observation suggests that while respondents may perceive AI as not particularly easy to use, they still find it remarkably useful within the realm of teaching. The disparity in means underscores the nuanced nature of teachers' attitudes toward AI, indicating a recognition of its utility despite potential challenges in terms of ease of use.

Significant Relationship between Profile of Respondents and their Acceptability Level on AI

Table 8. *Significant Relationship between Profile of Respondents and their Acceptability Level on AI*

<i>Relationship</i>	<i>R-value</i>	<i>P- value</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Age and AI acceptability level	0.31	.051571	Not Significant at $p > 0.05$
Sex and AI acceptability level	0.19	.240277	Not Significant at $p > 0.05$
Level of Technological Capability and AI acceptability level	0.42	.006973.	Significant at $p < 0.05$

The findings presented in Table 5 reveal that there is no statistically significant correlation between the age and sex of the participants and their perceived acceptability of AI. This implies that educators' perspectives on the utilization of AI are not contingent on their gender or age. Regardless of whether a teacher is male or female, younger or older, their attitude towards AI remains consistent. These results align with previous studies conducted by Ahmad (2019), Almousa (2020), and Darayseh (2023), all of which similarly found no significant differences in the computed results based on gender and age. Darayseh (2023) specifically noted that the lack of significant difference in teachers' adoption of AI regarding gender and age could be attributed to the similarity in circumstances and abilities among teachers, leading to a unified acceptance of technological tools like AI.

In contrast, a noteworthy observation emerges from the preceding table, emphasizing the substantial impact of technological proficiency on the acceptability level of AI. As elucidated in the aforementioned table, it becomes evident that the level of technological competency plays a crucial role in shaping the perceived usefulness and ease of utilizing AI tools. This observation is in line with current research findings by Odekeye (2023) and theoretical perspectives on technological skills, suggesting that individuals with a natural aptitude for technology are more likely to experience greater ease in managing and utilizing technological tools and resources. Recognizing this influential factor underscores the importance of educators acquiring and honing their technological competencies to facilitate a smoother and more efficient integration of AI in teaching.

Conclusions

Educators have positive acceptability level on AI utilization on teaching, in terms of usefulness. They find AI tools helpful in doing task quickly and finding access to variety of learning resources.

Educators have negative acceptability level on AI utilization on teaching, in terms of Ease of Use. They find the interface easy to understand, but disagree on being able to be skillful in using it in the context of teaching.

There is significant difference on the acceptability level on AI utilization in terms of usefulness and ease of use.

Age and sex have no significant relationship or impact on the perspective of the educators on AI utilization.

Educators' level of technological capability has significant impact on the perspective of the educators on AI utilization.

Based on the summary of findings and conclusion mentioned above, the researchers recommend the follow:

Establish a structured resource development program by allocating funds to manage the operation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) software solutions, providing training and assistance to faculty members.

Provide physical and software resources to educators, like unlimited internet and subscription to AI tools, in order to promote utilization of AI in doing tasks.

Conduct in-depth study on the modifying factors and variables like self-efficacy, perceived risks, social norms which can directly affect acceptability level of AI on educational context.

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